

UDC 711.455(477.86)
DOI: 10.31866/2616-7468.3.2.2020.219713

METHODOLOGY AND SCIENTIFIC SUBSTANTIATION OF RESORT TERRITORY “RAFAYLOVA” DESIGN IN IVANO-FRANKIVSK REGION

Volodymyr Klapchuk,
*Ph.D. hab. (History), Professor,
Vasyl Stefanyk Precarpathian
National University,
Ivano-Frankivsk, Ukraine,
volodymyr_klapchuk@ukr.net
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1788-794X>
© Klapchuk V., 2020*

Lesia Polova,
*Ph.D. in Pedagogical Science,
Vasyl Stefanyk Precarpathian National University,
Ivano-Frankivsk, Ukraine,
polyovy@ukr.net
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2971-5993>
© Polova L., 2020*

Alexandr Novosiolov,
*Ph.D. in History,
Vasyl Stefanyk Precarpathian National University,
Ivano-Frankivsk, Ukraine,
novo_a@ukr.net
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1407-4508>
© Novosiolov O., 2020*

The topicality. Taking into account the natural, economic, scientific and technical potentials available in the Carpathian region, the strategic goal of perspective development of the territory is to create an effective territorial-recreational system on the basis of optimal use of these resources, which will ensure the material well-being of the population and environmental safety of the area. It is important to expand the potential of TC “Bukovel” for international competitions of the highest level.

The purpose of the study is a theoretical justification for the design and zoning of the resort area on the example of the resort “Rafaylova” within the lands of Bystrytsya village council of Ivano-Frankivsk region.

Research methodology. The study tested an algorithm for the integrated use of a number of methods and techniques: general geographic, cartographic, space photography, zoning of environmental and urban systems, and others.

Results. Zoning of the territory of Bystrytsya village council by functional purpose was carried out. The zone of stationary recreation – 4925.1 hectares is allocated; regulated recreation area – 9046.3 ha (including 818.6 ha – NPF facilities); ski area – 5001.4 hectares; nature reserve fund – 2439.7 ha (another 818.6 ha of NPF objects – as a part of the zone of regulated recreation); lands of settlements – 795.4 hectares; the area of resort management – 5,5 hectares.

The administrative part of the resort “Rafaylova” (total area 55 150.2 m²) is divided into the following operational and tactical areas: administrative building is 661.2 m²; parking is 985 m²; sports ground is 4624.6 m²; garage is 4289.1 m²; garden (rock garden) is 796 m²; pump room is 38.7 m²; garden (arboretum) is 40,816.6 m²; household waste collection site is 12.2 m².

Conclusions. Functional zoning of the territory of Bystrytsya village council has been carried out. The resort area of “Rafaylov” will include: 221 tourist hotel and hotel complex; 2143 chalets, 368 locked cottages, 103 restaurants, 31 shops, 23 rental outlets, 10 medical facilities, 6 banking institutions, 1 service station, 3 multi-level parking lots, 45 parking lots, etc.

Keywords: rafailova, resort, hotel, chalet, cottage, restaurant, zoning, recreation.

The topicality of the problem

Formulation of the problem. The Carpathian region is traditionally a region where the prospects of the recreational and tourist sphere were and remain one of the best in Ukraine, and the existing long-term experience and experience in the field of recreation is a significant prerequisite for determining the sphere of recreation and tourism as a priority in the region.

Taking into account the natural, economic, scientific and technical potentials available in this area, as well as its historical and geographical features, the strategic goal of the long-term development of the territory is to, to create an effective territorial and recreational system based on the optimal use of natural, material, technical, labor and intellectual resources, which will ensure the material well-being of the population and environmental security of the Carpathian region.

It is important to expand the potential of TC "Bukovel" for international competitions of the highest level.

As the subject of territorial planning of resort zones from practical review is little studied, the presented research contains elements of **scientific novelty**.

The purpose of the article is a theoretical justification of the functional zoning of the resort "Rafaylova" on the lands of Bystrytsya village council of Ivano-Frankivsk region, as well as a study of the design of the projected facility for the competitive and highly efficient resort formation. To achieve this goal, a number of methods were used (general geographical, cartographic, space photography, zoning of environmental and urban systems, etc.), which in a logical combination made it possible to carry out a comprehensive zoning of administrative entities for the needs of the resort business.

The object of the study is the territory of Bystrytsya village council of Ivano-Frankivsk region, the territory and design of the resort management, and **the subject of the study** is its functional zoning for the needs of territorial planning of the resort.

The main issues of establishment and organization of resort areas and resorts are provided by the Law of Ukraine "On Resorts" (Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine, 2000). An important element of the legal regulation of protection and use of natural areas is the establishment of the object of such regulation is the definition of "resort", "health" or "recreational" area. Such concepts are defined in Art. 47 of the Land Code of Ukraine (Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine, 2001), Art. 62 of the Water Code of Ukraine (Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine, 1995), Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine of December 11, 1996 (Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine, 1996).

Research methodology. Theoretical substantiation of designing of the resort territory has led to development of own algorithm of methodical and methodological approaches used at territorial zoning of both separate settlements, and at functional zoning of territories of nature reserve fund.

The basis for declaring natural areas as resorts is the availability of natural medical resources and the necessary infrastructure for their operation and organization of human treatment. To do this, it is necessary to take organizational measures in accordance with the Laws of Ukraine "On Resorts" (Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine, 2000), "On State Ecological Expertise" (Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine, 2018) and "On Ensuring Sanitary and Epidemic Welfare" (Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine, 1994).

Urban planning documentation regulating construction on the territory of the resort is developed in accordance with the Law "On Fundamentals of Urban Planning"

(Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine, 1992a), “On Fundamentals of Social Protection of Disabled People in Ukraine” (Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine, 1991) and other bylaws state ecological and sanitary-hygienic examinations.

In sanatorium-resort zones, according to the current legislation of Ukraine, placement of the enterprises polluting atmospheric air, water space, detrimentally influencing flora and fauna is forbidden. Particular attention in such areas should be paid to the creation of rational transport arteries and roadside infrastructure, their provision with an environmentally friendly complex of engineering structures and equipment. This is critical in the design of the Gorgan mountain resort.

An important element of the planning of sanatorium-resort areas is the location of sources of supply of raw materials and service personnel near the settlements. When designing a resort area, the restrictions provided by Ukrainian legislation and bylaws of the state are taken into account.

The main task to achieve the goal of the study is the choice of methodological tools and the most effective research methods. Therefore, it is necessary to adapt existing research methods and methodological approaches that will ultimately have the greatest effect.

The following methods were used in the reconnaissance work: empirical research is observation (study of the general situation in the village of Bystritsa, natural, cultural, historical and infrastructural resources); comparison (differences between Bystrytsia village and neighboring villages were established, strengths and weaknesses of the project were identified, competitive environment was analyzed); measurement (establishment of morphometric indicators of a relief for needs of construction of a ski resort, definition of the technical and economic substantiation (TEP) of building of a site and the description of constructive features of a climatic resort); experiment (comparative analysis of hypsometric and morphometric indicators, microclimatic features with the resort of Bukovel). In general, for the territorial planning of the resort, these methods allow you to navigate the area, to consider the strategy and tactical schemes, the order of planning and zoning of the territory.

Methods of abstraction, analysis and synthesis contributed to the isolation and further integration of certain indicators or criteria for a specific research area.

The method of idealization makes it possible to design a climatic resort and its main buildings on the ground, to adapt the conditions of existing resorts in the Eastern Carpathians to the specific conditions of the village Bystritsa.

The system method using a structural-logical approach made it possible to carry out a comprehensive analysis of the collected materials into a holistic system and draw a conclusion about the possibility / impossibility, need / reality of creating a resort in the Bystritsa village council.

Based on the territory zoning, establishing the features of the construction of a climatic / ski resort, analysis of competitiveness, rationality, economic effect, you can design the core of the resort area: the resort “Rafaylova”, which includes: administrative building is resort management; car parking; playground; garage; garden (rock garden and arboretum); pump room; playground; sanitary facility (household waste collection point).

Zoning (zoning) of the territory of Bystrytsya village council was carried out in accordance with the “Methodology of preparation and content of the zoning plan (Zoning)”, approved by the decision of the Scientific and Technical Council of the Ministry of Regional Development, Construction and Housing of Ukraine dated 09.12.2015 № 77 (Ministry of Regional Development, Construction and Housing of Ukraine, 2015), Master Plan village

Bystritsa, afforestation plans of Nadvirna forestry, state building codes DBN B.1.1-15: 2012 “Composition and content of the general plan of the settlement” (Panchenko and others 2012), DBN 360-92 ** “Urban bilding”. “Planning and Development of Urban and Rural Settlements”(State Committee of Ukraine for Urban Planning and Architecture, 1992), other state norms, standards and rules (Dyuzhev, 2015, pp. 129–139).

The materials of the zoning plan are developed using the updated cartographic basis in digital form as sets of profile geospatial data in the state geodetic coordinate system USK-2000.

Zoning was developed in accordance with the Law of Ukraine “On Regulation of Urban Development”, state building codes, other laws and regulations governing the use of land, real estate and cultural heritage protection, preservation of the environment; land use taking into account the urban features of the village. Bystrytsia, “Methods of compiling and content of Zoning”, decisions of urban planning documentation and “Guidelines on the composition and content of the zoning plan (Zoning)” (State Committee of Ukraine for Urban Planning and Architecture, 1992; Ukrainian State Research Institute of Urban Design “Dipromisto”, 2012; Urban Planning Department and Architecture of Kyivgenplan, 2015).

The structure of territorial zones is established in zoning. They are determined by the main functional purpose and include areas of public, residential, landscape and recreational, communal, industrial, historical and cultural purposes, the territory of transport infrastructure, nature reserve fund.

Planning restrictions include regulatory, conservation restrictions, restrictions on natural, man-made phenomena and environmental protection.

Research results.

With the help of space images, the boundaries of the Bystrytsya village council were established on the area of 22,207.9 ha (Fig. 1), according to the zoning method, the zoning of this territory by functional purpose was carried out. The whole territory is divided into five zones:

- stationary recreation area – 4925.1 hectares;
- regulated recreation area – 9046.3 ha (including 818.6 ha – NPF facilities);
- ski area – 5001.4 hectares;
- nature reserve fund – 2439.7 ha (another 818.6 ha of NPF objects – as a part of the zone of regulated recreation);
- lands of settlements – 795.4 hectares;
- area of resort management (further – building) – 5,5 hectares (55 150,2 m²);
- stationary recreation area with a total area of 4925.1 hectares, designed to accommodate hotels, motels, campsites and other facilities for visitor services. It prohibits any economic activity not related to the purpose of this functional area or may adversely affect the state of natural complexes and objects (Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine, 1992b);
- the zone of regulated recreation covers an area of 9046.3 ha and includes 8227.7 ha of lands of the state forest fund and 818.6 ha of NPF objects of Ukraine of local significance. Within the zone, short-term recreation and health improvement of the population, inspection of especially picturesque and memorable places are carried out. The installation and appropriate equipment of tourist routes and ecological trails is

A protected regime has been declared in the territory of this zone. It is designed to protect and restore the most valuable natural complexes, and its use is determined in accordance with the requirements established for nature reserves (Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine, 1992b).

The ski area covers a total area of 5001.4 hectares, of which about 1,200 hectares are allocated to ski resorts and infrastructure.

The land of settlements includes 795.4 hectares of territory under construction and rural infrastructure. It includes private estates, local governments, educational institutions, health care, trade, catering, religious facilities, road network and roadside infrastructure, etc.

The ski area of the resort will cover an area of 1,200 hectares within the current Richansky (750 hectares) and Dovzhynetsky (350 hectares) forests of Nadvirna forestry. A promising network of buildings and facilities is shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Promising network of buildings and facilities of the resort “Rafaylova”

Hotels, rooms	18 760
Tourist hotels and hotel complexes	221
Chalet cottages	2143
Cottages are blocked	368
Public buildings, including:	173
food establishments	103
shops	31
rental points	23
medical institutions	10
banks	6
Transport infrastructure, including:	48
service stations	1
multilevel parking lots	3
structured parking	45
Accumulating pond	3
Sewage treatment plant	1

The estate of the resort management is located within the lands of the settlement on the area of 5.5 hectares.

The administrative part of the resort “Rafaylova” (total area 55 150.2 m²) is divided into the following operational and tactical areas: administrative building is 661.2 m²; parking is 985 m²; sports ground is 4624.6 m²; garage is 4289.1 m²; garden (rock garden) is 796 m²; pump room is 38.7 m²; garden (arboretum) is 40,816.6 m²; household waste collection site is 12.2 m² (Fig. 2).

On the projected area it is planned to place the main building of the resort with the following premises: 1st floor are lobby, reception, office space, information center, museum, library, staff room, storage room, bathrooms; 2nd floor are kitchen, restaurant, library, staff room, bathrooms; 3rd floor are living rooms for staff and guests (16 pcs.) for 50 places; basement.

Fig. 2. Scheme of territorial organization of resort management

Source: own development

Conclusions. The authors have developed a method of complex functional zoning of the territory of administrative-territorial formation, territorial planning of the resort

area and design of resort management on the example of the resort area “Rafaylova” in Ivano-Frankivsk region.

On the territory of Bystrytsya village council, according to the method developed by the authors, five zones have been identified according to their functional purpose: inpatient recreation; regulated recreation; skiing; nature reserve fund; land settlements. The administrative part of the resort area “Rafaylova” with a total area of over 5.5 hectares is divided into the following operational and tactical areas: administrative building; parking; playground; garage; garden (rock garden); pump room; garden (arboretum); household waste collection site.

REFERENCES

- Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine. (1996). *Pro zatverdzhennia pereliku vodnykh obiektiv, shcho vidnosiatsia do katehorii likuvalnykh* [About the statement of the list of the water objects belonging to a category of medical]. Resolution № 1499 of December 11, 1996. <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/1499-96-%D0%BF> [in Ukrainian].
- Departament mistobuduvannia ta arkhitektury KO “Kyivhenplan”. (2015). *Plan zonuvannia terytorii (zoninh) tsentralnoi planivalnoi zony mista Kyieva (proekt)* [Zoning plan of the territory (zoning) of the central planning zone of the city of Kyiv (project)] (Vol. 1). Kyivska miska derzhavna administratsiia [in Ukrainian].
- Derzhavnyi komitet Ukrainy u spravakh mistobuduvannia i arkhitektury. (1992). *Mistobuduvannia. Planuvannia ta zabudova miskykh ta silskykh poselen. DBN 360-92*** [Urban planning. Planning and construction of urban and rural settlements. DBN 360-92**]. <https://kga.gov.ua/files/doc/normy-derjavny/dbn/Mistobuduvannja-Planuvannja-i-zabudova-miskyh-i-silskyh-poselen-DBN-360-92.pdf> [in Ukrainian].
- Diuzhev, S. A. (2015). Zmist planu zonuvannia (zoninhu) yak mistobudivnoho dokumenta mistobudivnoho rehulivannia. [The content of the zoning plan (zoning) as a document of the town-planning document of town-planning regulation]. *Mistobuduvannia ta terytorialne planuvannia, 1*, 129–139 [in Ukrainian].
- Klapchuk, V. M. (2007). *Pryrodno-rekreatsiini resursy Ukrainskykh Karpat* [Natural and recreational resources of the Ukrainian Carpathians]. Foliant [in Ukrainian].
- Ministerstvo rehionalnoho rozvytku, budivnytstva ta zhytlovo-komunalnoho hospodarstva Ukrainy. (2015). *Pro proekt Metodyky skladannia ta zmistu planu zonuvannia terytorii (zoninhu) m. Kyieva* [About the project of the Methodology of drawing up and the maintenance of the plan of zoning of the territory (zoning) of Kiev]. Decision of the Scientific and Technical Council (in working order) № 77 of December 9, 2015. <https://www.minregion.gov.ua/wp-content/uploads/2016/01/Rishennya-77-Metodiki-skladannya-ta-zmistu-planu-zonuvannya-teritoriyi-zoningu-m.-Kiyeva.pdf> [in Ukrainian].
- Panchenko, T., Protsenko, S., Onyshchenko, V., Khrystiuk, M., & Sokovnina, N. (2012). *Sklad ta zmist heneralnoho planu naselenoho punktu. DBN B.1.1-15:2012* [Composition and content of the general plan of the settlement. DBN B.1.1-15: 2012]. Minrehion Ukrainy [in Ukrainian].
- Ukrainian State Scientific-Research Institute of Urban Design “DIPROMISTO” (2012, June 1). *Nastanova pro sklad ta zmist planu zonuvannia terytorii (zoninh). DSTU-N B B.1.1-12:2011* [Guidelines on the composition and content of the zoning plan (zoning). DSTU-N B B.1.1-12: 2011]. <http://dbn.co.ua/load/normativy/dstu/5-1-0-1010> [in Ukrainian].
- Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine. (1991). *Pro osnovy sotsialnoi zakhyshchenosti osib z invalidnistiu v Ukraini* [On the basics of social protection of persons with disabilities in Ukraine]. Law of

- Ukraine № 876-XII of March 21, 1991. <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/875-12> [in Ukrainian].
- Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine. (1992a). *Pro osnovy mistobuduvannia [On the basics of urban planning]*. Law of Ukraine № 2781-XII of November 16, 1992. <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/2780-12> [in Ukrainian].
- Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine. (1992b). *Pro pryrodno-zapovidnyi fond [About the nature reserve fund]*. Law of Ukraine № 2457-XII of June 16, 1992. <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/2456-12> [in Ukrainian].
- Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine. (1994). *Pro zabezpechennia sanitarnoho ta epidemichnoho blahopoluchchia naseleennia [On ensuring the sanitary and epidemic well-being of the population]*. Law of Ukraine № 4005-XII of February 24, 1994. <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/4004-12> [in Ukrainian].
- Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine. (1995). *Vodnyi kodeks Ukrainy [Water Code of Ukraine]*. Document № 214/95-VR from Juni 6, 1995. <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/213/95-%D0%B2%D1%80> [in Ukrainian].
- Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine. (2000). *Pro kurorty [About resorts]*. Law of Ukraine № 2026-III of October 5, 2000. <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/2026-14> [in Ukrainian].
- Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine. (2001). *Zemelnyi kodeks Ukrainy [Land Code of Ukraine]*. Document № 2768-III of October 25, 2001. <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/2768-14> [in Ukrainian].
- Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine. (2018). *Pro stratehichnu ekolohichnu otsinku [About strategic ecological assessment]*. Law of Ukraine № 2354-VIII from March 20, 2018. <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/2354-19> [in Ukrainian].

The article was received on November 09, 2020

УДК 711.455(477.86)

Володимир Клапчук,

доктор історичних наук, професор,
ДВНЗ «Прикарпатський національний
університет
імені Василя Стефаника»,
Івано-Франківськ, Україна,
volodymyr_klapchuk@ukr.net
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1788-794X>

Леся Польова,

кандидат педагогічних наук, доцент,
ДВНЗ «Прикарпатський національний
університет
імені Василя Стефаника»,
Івано-Франківськ, Україна,
polovu@ukr.net
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2971-5993>

Олександр Новосолов,

кандидат історичних наук, доцент,
ДВНЗ «Прикарпатський національний
університет
імені Василя Стефаника»,
Івано-Франківськ, Україна,
novo_a@ukr.net
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1407-4508>

МЕТОДОЛОГІЯ І НАУКОВЕ ОБҐРУНТУВАННЯ ПРОЄКТУВАННЯ КУРОРТНОЇ ТЕРИТОРІЇ «РАФАЙЛОВА» В ІВАНО-ФРАНКІВСЬКІЙ ОБЛАСТІ

Актуальність проблеми. З урахуванням наявних у Карпатському регіоні природного, економічного, наукового і технічного потенціалів стратегічна мета перспективного розвитку території полягає в тому, щоб на основі оптимального використання цих ресурсів створити ефективну територіально-рекреаційну систему, яка забезпечить матеріальний добробут населення і екологічну безпеку місцевості. Актуальним є розширення потенціалу ТК «Буковель» для проведення міжнародних змагань найвищого рівня.

Мета дослідження – теоретичне обґрунтування проєктування та зонування курортної території на прикладі курорту «Рафайлова» в межах земель Бистрицької сільської ради Івано-Франківської області.

Методика досліджень. У дослідженні апробовано алгоритм комплексного використання ряду методів і методик: загальногеографічний, картографічний, космофотознімків, зонування природоохоронних і урбанізованих систем та ін.

Результати. Проведено зонування території Бистрицької сільської ради за функціональним призначенням. Виокремлено зону стаціонарної рекреації – 4925,1 га; зону регульованої рекреації – 9046,3 га (у т. ч. 818,6 га – об'єкти ПЗФ); гірськолижну зону – 5001,4 га; природно-заповідний фонд – 2439,7 га (ще 818,6 га об'єктів ПЗФ – у складі зони регульованої рекреації); землі населених пунктів – 795,4 га; площу курортного управління – 5,5 га.

Адміністративна частина курорту «Рафайлова» (загальна площа 55 150,2 м²) поділена на наступні оперативно-тактичні ділянки: адміністративна будівля – 661,2 м²; автостоянка –

985 м²; спортивний майданчик – 4624,6 м²; гараж – 4289,1 м²; сад (альпінарій) – 796 м²; бювет – 38,7 м²; сад (дендропарк) – 40 816,6 м²; майданчик збору побутових відходів – 12,2 м².

Висновки. Здійснено функціональне зонування території Бистрицької сільської ради. Курортна територія «Рафайлова» включатиме: 221 туристичний готель і готельний комплекс; 2143 шале, 368 зблокованих котеджів, 103 заклади харчування, 31 заклад торгівлі, 23 прокатні пункти, 10 медичних закладів, 6 банківських установ, 1 станцію технічного обслуговування, 3 багаторівневі паркінги, 45 автостоянок та ін.

Ключові слова: Рафайлова, курорт, готель, шале, котедж, заклад харчування, зонінг, рекреація.

УДК 711.455(477.86)

Владимир Кларчук,

доктор исторических наук, профессор,
ГВУЗ «Прикарпатский национальный
университет
имени Василия Стефаника»,
Ивано-Франковск, Украина,
volodymyr_klapchuk@ukr.net
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1788-794X>

Леся Полевая,

кандидат педагогических наук, доцент,
ГВУЗ «Прикарпатский национальный
университет
имени Василия Стефаника»,
Ивано-Франковск, Украина,
polyovyy@ukr.net
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2971-5993>

Александр Новоселов,

кандидат исторических наук, доцент,
ГВУЗ «Прикарпатский национальный
университет
имени Василия Стефаника»,
Ивано-Франковск, Украина,
novo_a@ukr.net
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1407-4508>

МЕТОДОЛОГИЯ И НАУЧНОЕ ОБОСНОВАНИЕ ПРОЕКТИРОВАНИЯ КУРОРТНОЙ ТЕРРИТОРИИ «РАФАЙЛОВА» В ИВАНО-ФРАНКОВСКОЙ ОБЛАСТИ

Актуальность темы. С учетом существующих природного, экономического, научного и технического потенциалов стратегическая цель перспективного развития территории заключается в том, чтобы на основании оптимального использования этих ресурсов создать эффективную территориально-рекреационную систему, которая создаст материальное благополучие населения и экологическую безопасность Карпатского региона. Актуальным является расширение потенциала ТК «Буковель» для проведения международных соревнований наивысшего уровня.

Целью статьи является теоретическое обоснование проектирования и зонирования курортной территории на примере курорта «Рафайлова» в пределах земель Бистрицкого сельского совета Ивано-Франковской области.

Методика досліджень. В дослідженні апробовано алгоритм комплексного використання ряду методів і методик: общегеографического, картографического, космодотоснімків, зонирования природоохранных і урбанізованих систем і др.

Результати. Проведено зонирование території Быстрицкого сільського совета по функціональному назначению. Выделены зона стационарної рекреації – 4925,1 га; зона регулірованої рекреації – 9046,3 га (в т. ч. 818,6 га – об'єкти ПЗФ); горнолыжная зона – 5001,4 га; природно-заповідний фонд – 2439,7 га (еще 818,6 га об'єктів ПЗФ – в составе зоны регулірованої рекреації); землі населених пунктів – 795,4 га; площа курортного управління – 5,5 га.

Адміністративная часть курорта «Рафайлова» (общая площадь 55 150,2 м²) поделена на следующие оперативно-тактические участки: адміністративное строение – 661,2 м²; автостоянка – 985 м²; спортивная площадка – 4624,6 м²; гараж – 4289,1 м²; сад (альпинарий) – 796 м²; бювет – 38,7 м²; сад (дендропарк) – 40 816,6 м²; площадка сбора бытовых отходов – 12,2 м².

Выводы. Проведено функціональне зонирование території Быстрицкого сільського совета. Курортная территория «Рафайлова» будет включать: 221 туристическую гостиницу и отельный комплекс; 2143 шале, 368 сблокированных коттеджей, 103 пункта питания, 31 заведение торговли, 23 прокатных пункта, 10 медицинских заведений, 6 банковских заведений, 1 станцию технического обслуживания, 3 многоуровневых паркинга, 45 автостоянок и др.

Ключевые слова: Рафайлова, курорт, гостиница, шале, коттедж, пункт питания, зонинг, рекреація.